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Methodology F-WORD

Anthropological perspective will guide the project analysis, based on ethnography and the observation of practices of everyday social reproduction. Fieldwork will be carried by the three experienced post-docs and the PI, and fieldwork location will be decided by the team after the diachronic analysis and the preliminary fieldtrip of the PI to the country partner. The post-docs and the PI will keep regularly in contact, and the PI will join the post-docs two times during fieldwork, at the beginning for explorative interviews at informed interlocutors (professors, historian, journalist), and for intermediary following and participation to events. Anthropological attention to practices of everyday life is entangled with its attention to processes of meaning-formation from an emic perspective, and to processes of social reproduction. This proves a key tool in unpacking the “otherness” process driving people to see fascists only as monstrous, insane and extraneous to ‘normal’ society (Littell 2006, Pasięka 2019). Meanwhile, ethnographic research on fascism necessitate to engage with ethical and political issues emerging from the specific political actuality (and past history) of the subject area of research. This project engages with the necessity to unveil the multiple presence of forms of threat and violence in fascist context, and relation of discrimination and racism needs to be assumed when deciding to collaborate during research process and with whom. This project proposes to use feminist ethnography as a paradigm of research to assume the “eminently political” condition of social science research (Bourdieu Wacquant 1992, Bourdieu 2003), especially when engaging with an anthropology of fascism. Researchers shall be aware and scientifically cognizant of their own positioning and presence during ethnography. Recent developments in feminist ethnographic literature (Schrock 2018, Davis Craven 2016) suggest a new direction for systemically engaging with the epistemological implications of positionality during fieldwork relations. Feminist ethnography is not a data collection method as surveys, fieldwork notes, interviews, and observation; rather, it is a methodology for interrogating such data (Davis Craven 2016). This project uses a multi-part methodology involving interdisciplinary tools and intersectionality. Intersectionality is an established tool of research, coming from feminist analysis. This analytical perspective is key for revealing the multi-faceted character of identity, representation, oppression, and more. Martina Avanza (2019) has also demonstrated that intersectionality is an essential tool in conducting ethnography in politically thick contexts. In this proposed research, intersectionality will provide the analytical lens for unpacking the word “youth” to consider its multiple situated aspects. How is the appropriation of European history for youth from outside Europe, from ex-colonial countries or others? And how does gender influence reception and use – or opposition to – fascist ideas and symbols? How do different neighbourhood settings inform the class composition of youth groups training, and how does class intersect with images of the past and future? To consider the axis of age, the researchers will also interview sport instructors as well as teachers and family members. The research will be organised following Pilkington’s mode of progressing from surveys to ethnography (Pilkington et al. 2018) as tools for accessing the field. This will proceed by drafting surveys and forming the team during the preparatory year (M2); subsequently, each post-doc will adapt the survey to his or her specific field site. Ethnography goes beyond merely collecting quantifiable data to also combine daily observation and reflection on a context. The anthropological attention to daily life practices in search of meanings may be attained through intense ethnographic fieldwork in which the researcher builds relationships and participates daily in the context of investigation (De Sardan 2015). Martial arts and combat sports events, gyms and related public occasions are the concrete sites and critical junctions in which F-WORD team will establish contact and relationship with young people in three cities in Belgium, Italy and Poland. Loic Wacquant has demonstrated the analytical richness of doing ethnography on the daily life of boxers (Wacquant 2009): this represents a solid argument for concentrating on combat sports and martial arts, but in this project the object of observation and analysis is not daily life inside the boxing or training rooms or sport itself. Rather,

these contexts are used as critical junctions for positioning the research and encountering the circulation and appropriation of fascist traces and meanings among the young people who frequent these spaces. Training will be a participatory way for ethnographers to deepen their relationships with young people. The survey will be used at the beginning of the fieldwork, together with the mapping involved in the background analysis, to identify which neighbourhoods and gyms researchers should focus on. Finally, the 10-month-long ethnographic fieldwork periods will be followed by comparative data sharing among team members. The PI and team will not look for the reproduction of specific attitudes or phenomenological appearances at this point. F-WORD instead seeks to develop an in- depth understanding of the diffusion of an ideological system, to grasp the existence of a logic (Kapferer [1988] 2012) embedded in the way fascism emerges and is signified.